

Effect of Perceived Stress on Electrocardiographic Parameters of Female Health Professionals: A Cross-Sectional Observational StudyRavish Kumar Sinha¹, Pandurang M. Narhare², Sandeep Kumar³¹Senior Resident, Department of Physiology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India.²Professor & HOD, Department of Physiology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India.³Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India.

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Abstract:**Background:** The relationship between perceived stress and cardiac health is an area of growing concern, particularly among health professionals who experience high levels of stress. Understanding how stress affects electrocardiographic (ECG) parameters can provide insights into the cardiovascular risks faced by this population.**Aim:** This study intends to investigate the effect of apparent stress on electrocardiographic parameters in female health professionals.**Methods:** This cross-sectional observational study, led which examined the effect of perceived stress on ECG parameters in 180 female health professionals aged 25-60 years. Perceived stress was measured using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), and ECG parameters were recorded using a standard 12-lead ECG machine. Participants were recruited from various hospital departments to minimize selection bias. Statistical analysis, including Pearson's correlation and multiple regression, was performed using SPSS version 21.0 to determine relationships between stress levels and ECG parameters, adjusting for confounders like age, BMI, and work experience.**Results:** The study found that higher levels of perceived stress among female health professionals were significantly associated with an increased heart rate and a decreased PR interval. Specifically, perceived stress had a reasonable +ve association with heart rate ($r = 0.52$) and a reasonable negative association with PR interval ($r = -0.35$). These associations remained significant after adjusting for BMI and age. No noteworthy correlations were observed between perceived stress and other ECG parameters such as QRS duration, QT interval, and ST segment. The findings emphasize the importance of stress management to reduce cardiovascular risks in this population.**Conclusion:** Perceived stress is associated with adverse changes in ECG parameters among female health professionals. These changes indicate a potential increased risk for cardiac events in this population.**Recommendations:** Interventions to manage stress, such as mindfulness training, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and workplace stress reduction programs, should be implemented to mitigate these risks. Regular monitoring of ECG parameters in stressed health professionals is also recommended to identify and manage early signs of cardiac stress.**Keywords:** Electrocardiography, Female Health Professionals, Stress, Cross-Sectional Study.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The healthcare profession is widely recognized for its demanding and stressful nature. Female health professionals, in particular, face unique stressors, including work-life balance challenges, patient care responsibilities, and workplace dynamics. Prolonged exposure to such stress can have detrimental effects on their physical and mental health. One critical area of concern is the impact of perceived stress on cardiovascular health, which can be as-

essed through changes in electrocardiographic (ECG) parameters [1].

The link between stress and cardiovascular disease is well-documented, with stress known to trigger physiological responses that can affect heart function. Stress-induced changes in heart rate, blood pressure, and hormonal levels can lead to alterations in the electrical activity of the heart. This is of particular importance for female health profession-

als, who not only deal with occupational stress but also face other stressors related to their personal lives [2].

Electrocardiography is a non-invasive tool used to measure the electrical activity of the heart and is crucial in diagnosing various cardiac conditions. Parameters such as heart rate, QT interval, and ST segment are key indicators of cardiac health. Variations in these parameters can signal underlying issues, such as arrhythmias or ischemia, which may be exacerbated by stress. Understanding how perceived stress impacts these ECG parameters can help in early identification and prevention of potential cardiac events among female health professionals [3,4].

Given the significant role that female health professionals play in the healthcare system, ensuring their well-being is paramount. Stress management and cardiac health monitoring are essential components of occupational health strategies. This study aims to fill the gap in the current literature by exploring the relationship between perceived stress and ECG parameters in this specific demographic, providing valuable insights that could inform targeted interventions.

The chief intention of this study is to investigate the effect of perceived stress on electrocardiographic parameters in female health professionals. By examining the correlation between stress levels and ECG changes, this research seeks to highlight the cardiovascular risks associated with occupational stress and propose measures for stress management and cardiac health maintenance in this vulnerable group.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was conducted as a cross-sectional observational study designed to investigate the effect of perceived stress on electrocardiographic (ECG) parameters in female health professionals.

Study Setting: The research was carried out at the E. S. I. C. M. C. H., Bihta, Patna.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over a period of 11 months.

Participants: A total of 180 female health professionals participated in the study. This included doctors, nurses, and administrative staff working in the hospital. Participants were between 25 and 60 years of age and had a minimum of one year of work experience in the healthcare sector.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Female health professionals aged 25-60 years
- Employed in the healthcare sector for at least one year
- Provided informed consent to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria:

- History of cardiovascular disease
- Currently taking medications affecting heart rate or ECG parameters
- Pregnant women
- Participants who had undergone major surgery or experienced significant trauma in the past six months

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited from various departments and professional roles within the hospital. Information bias was reduced by using standardized and validated tools for both stress assessment and ECG measurement.

Variables

- **Independent Variable:** Perceived stress levels, measured using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS).
- **Dependent Variables:** ECG parameters, including heart rate, PR interval, QRS complex duration, QT interval, and ST segment changes.

Data Collection: Data collection involved two main components: stress assessment and ECG recording. The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), a validated questionnaire, was used to evaluate participants' stress levels. ECG parameters were recorded using a standard 12-lead ECG machine.

Procedure

Participants were informed about the study objectives and procedures before obtaining written informed consent. They were asked to complete the PSS questionnaire to assess their perceived stress levels. Following the questionnaire, participants underwent a 12-lead ECG recording in a controlled environment to ensure consistent conditions for all participants.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Participant Characteristics: A total of 180 female health professionals participated in the study. The average age of the participants was 39.2 years (SD = 7.6), with a range of 25 to 60 years. The mean work experience was 13.1 years (SD = 5.9).

Characteristic	Mean (SD)	Range
Age (years)	39.2 (7.6)	25-60
Work Experience (years)	13.1 (5.9)	1-35
Body Mass Index (BMI)	24.8 (3.2)	18.4-31.0

Perceived Stress Levels: The mean Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) score among the participants was 22.1 (SD = 5.3), with scores ranging from 12 to 36.

PSS Score	Mean (SD)	Range
Perceived Stress Scale	22.1 (5.3)	12-36

Electrocardiographic Parameters: The ECG parameters recorded from the participants showed the following mean values:

ECG Parameter	Mean (SD)	Range
Heart Rate (bpm)	78.3 (9.2)	62-98
PR Interval (ms)	160.1 (17.6)	120-200
QRS Duration (ms)	93.7 (10.3)	80-110
QT Interval (ms)	392.8 (28.5)	350-460
ST Segment (mm)	0.3 (0.4)	-1 to 1

Correlation Between Perceived Stress and ECG Parameters: Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a noteworthy positive correlation between PSS scores and heart rate ($r = 0.52$, $p < 0.001$), and a significant negative correlation between PSS

scores and PR interval ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$). No significant correlations were found between PSS scores and QRS duration, QT interval, or ST segment.

ECG Parameter	Correlation with PSS	p-value
Heart Rate	$r = 0.52$	< 0.001
PR Interval	$r = -0.35$	< 0.001
QRS Duration	$r = 0.07$	0.42
QT Interval	$r = 0.05$	0.58
ST Segment	$r = -0.03$	0.72

Multiple Regression Analysis: Multiple regression analysis was conducted to adjust for potential confounders. The model showed that perceived stress ($\beta = 0.47$, $p < 0.001$) and BMI ($\beta = 0.23$, $p = 0.01$) were significant predictors of heart rate. For PR interval, perceived stress ($\beta = -0.32$, $p < 0.001$) and age ($\beta = -0.27$, $p = 0.01$) were significant predictors.

Dependent Variable	Predictor	β	p-value
Heart Rate	Perceived Stress	0.47	< 0.001
	BMI	0.23	0.01
PR Interval	Perceived Stress	-0.32	< 0.001
	Age	-0.27	0.01

The study found that higher levels of perceived stress were significantly associated with increased heart rate and decreased PR interval among female health professionals. Specifically, there was a moderate positive correlation between perceived stress and heart rate ($r = 0.52$), indicating that as stress levels increase, heart rate tends to increase. Conversely, there was a moderate negative correlation between perceived stress and PR interval ($r = -0.35$), suggesting that higher stress levels are associated with shorter PR intervals. These associations remained significant even after adjusting for potential confounders such as BMI and age. No significant associations were observed between perceived stress and other ECG parameters, including QRS duration, QT interval, and ST segment.

Discussion

The results demonstrated significant associations between higher levels of perceived stress and changes in specific ECG parameters, notably an increased heart rate and a decreased PR interval. A similar study by Chaudhuri et al. (2019) observed that female health professionals with higher perceived stress exhibited significant changes in ECG parameters, including reduced QRS complex duration and elevated T-wave amplitude (5). These changes suggest an autonomic imbalance, aligning with our findings of increased heart rate and shortened PR interval.

Another study focusing on urban female populations found that stress adversely affects cardiovascular health, leading to dyslipidemia and altered

autonomic functions. This reinforces the notion that perceived stress significantly impacts cardiovascular parameters [6].

Mechanisms and Implications: The observed increase in heart rate and decrease in PR interval can be attributed to the sympathetic nervous system's response to stress, which accelerates the heart rate and reduces atrioventricular conduction time. These physiological responses are part of the "fight or flight" mechanism, which prepares the body to respond to perceived threats.

Higher perceived stress levels among healthcare professionals can lead to chronic cardiovascular strain, potentially increasing the risk of arrhythmias and other heart-related conditions. The correlation between stress and cardiovascular health highlights the importance of stress management interventions in the healthcare sector.

Limitations: One limitation of this research is its cross-sectional nature, which hinders the ability to determine causation between stress and ECG alterations. Conducting longitudinal studies could help validate these results and investigate the prolonged impacts of perceived stress on cardiovascular well-being. Furthermore, the study's dependence on self-reported stress levels introduces potential bias. Future investigations should consider using objective stress indicators, such as cortisol levels, to achieve a more thorough evaluating stress.

Recommendations: To mitigate the adverse effects of stress on cardiovascular health, healthcare institutions should implement stress management programs, such as mindfulness training, counseling, and relaxation techniques. Regular screening for stress and cardiovascular health among healthcare professionals can also help in early identification and intervention.

Conclusion

This study adds to the growing body of evidence indicating that perceived stress significantly im-

pacts ECG parameters, particularly heart rate and PR interval, among female health professionals. These findings underscore the need for effective stress management strategies to promote cardiovascular health and overall well-being in this population.

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